

Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

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ABSTRACT: This study examined business education teaching strategies as a correlate of unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State Tertiary institutions. The business education strategies considered in this study were practical skills acquisition strategies, ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurial training strategies while the under-unemployment mitigation variables were, employability skills, entrepreneurial intention and rate of self/hired employment were examined. Seven research questions were raised and answered, while four null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 1028 business education students and graduates. The stratified sampling technique and purposive sampling techniques were adopted and the sample size was 397. A structured questionnaire was used and was validated by three experts. The overall Chronbach's Alpha value obtained for the instrument showed a reliability coefficient of 0.74. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) and Multivariate Linear Regression Analysis. The findings of the study revealed that there was a very highly positive correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and employability skills of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. Also, the study indicated that components of business education strategies mitigate unemployment among business education graduates in Delta State among others. It was concluded that the most significant components that mitigate unemployment are practical skills acquisition and entrepreneurship training strategies. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that stakeholders of business education programme should ensure that the students are properly engaged in practical training as it will boost their practical skills acquisition and invariably boost their employability skills which in turn will help to mitigate unemployment. The study has empirically established that, practical skills acquisition strategies is very highly correlated to employability skills of Business Education students in Delta state tertiary institutions.

KEYWORDS: Business Education, Entrepreneurial Training, Employability Skills, Teaching Strategies, Unemployment Mitigation, Self-Employment.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Unemployment has become a global dilemma presently confronting the world with the highest rate being recorded among third world nations. The challenge is becoming more complex and intricate in our nation Nigeria with a yearly turn-over of graduates from various tertiary institutions within the country into an already saturated labour market thereby increasing the existing large numbers of unemployed graduates.

According to the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023) in its third quarter report for 2023 pegged unemployment rate in the country at 5.0%, under a revised methodology yet unemployment was significantly higher at 12.3%, showing a high prevalence of vulnerable employment and inadequate work hours. Jhingan in Edeh and Udoikah (2018) opined that unemployment is one of the most sensitive and disturbing problem fighting against the development of contemporary Nigeria society. According to Okafor and Ibrahim (2016) Unemployment occurs when individuals who are qualified and willing to work cannot find jobs due to structural

Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

deficiencies. Given the above, this study was conducted to find out the reasons for the high level of unemployment rate among Business Education students who are supposed to be employed or be employers of labour by creating job for themselves and others.

The labour market can be described as supply of labour and demands for labour, for which employees provide supply and employers provide demand. It is an important component of every economy and is intricately intertwined markets for capital, goods, and services. The present world market place has taken a new turn with advancement of technology and innovations. Technological innovation has transformed the nature of production and trade, as industrialization has steadily evolve and become more capital-intensive, principally due to the discoveries of machineries and technology, as such, it has an overwhelming effect on the labour force as a result of efficiency that leads to productivity. The emergence of a new economic landscape which has been sharpened and formed by increase in productivity and output level, largely influenced by progress in technological innovations and inventions. As such it is only those who are prepared and equipped to meet with ever challenging and dynamic demands that are employable. This issue is more pronounced among Business Education students, who are expected to have both theoretical knowledge and practical skills that should enable them to secure jobs or become self-reliant after graduation.

Business Education, as a vocational discipline, aims to equip students with competencies in entrepreneurship, management, accounting, office practice, and information technology. Business education in the view of Ezenwanne (2020) is the aspect of tertiary education programme that involves general knowledge, vocational literacy and entrepreneurship. Ezenwanne postulated that business education offers her learners the opportunity to be vastly and in-depth ably knowledgeable in order to understand and meet with the demands of the contemporary work environment. In similar light Akpojotor and Chukwuemeke (2024) viewed business education from its philosophy that it is to provide individuals with relevant knowledge, skills and competencies to be self-reliant and economically self-sufficient for gainful employment meaningful living and to contribute to the development of society. With this philosophy, students who wish to pursue a career in business have opportunity to develop the said skills, abilities and understanding that enable them to enter, perform and progress in any business occupation after graduation from tertiary institutions. Business education provides students with practical skills and knowledge necessary for entrepreneurship and employment, thereby reducing unemployment. A cardinal goal of Business Education at higher institution level is to create self-employment for graduates after completion of academic quests. These competencies are crucial for mitigating unemployment state and over reliance on government jobs. These skills are designed to prepare graduates to either enter the workforce or start-up businesses. However, Business education programme is concerned with teaching skills, attitudes and knowledge necessary for a successful career in office and business world. Business education develops students with the basic education for a teaching career, entrepreneurship, business understanding, labour industry understanding, office environment procedures and vocational practices. Onajite (2016), opined that business education encompasses education programme for business, office occupation, economic understanding, entrepreneurship and it seeks to develop in the learner's basic skills for personal use in the future. The objectives of business education as high-lighted by Onajite (2016) are to facilitate the students to gain experience with skills and also to make available to students with necessary information about all aspects of business. Similarly Ordu and Abdulkarim (2020), stated business education is required by students in our modern-day world because it develops life skills for economic success and helps students to develop attitudes needed for career success. In view of the researchers, the relevance of business education in ensuring that students are adequately prepared, adapt and fit in into the ever demanding and dynamic labour market in Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized because of its potential in equipping recipients with relevant skills for self-employment.

Unfortunately the myopic mindset of these students relying on paid employment after graduation rather than utilizing the training, skills and experience acquired to set up businesses has become a bane among graduates of Business Education. However, high unemployment rate among Business Education graduates raises concerns about effectiveness of the current strategies used in Business Education programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions and lack of basic teaching aids and apparatus to facilitate a conducive learning environment. Okoro (2018) stated the need for provision of adequate laboratories for Business Education students, provision of sufficient classrooms for effective teaching of Business Education, improves student's attitudes towards skills acquisition through orientation and regular supervision of Business Education programme will help students to develop skills that will enable them setup their own business to curb unemployment.

Despite Delta State's abundance of human and natural resources, it is grappling with an increasing unemployment rate among graduates, even though multiple tertiary institutions offer Business Education programs. This scenario highlights a gap between the intended objectives of Business Education and the real-world results. As a result, it is crucial to assess the instructional methods used in teaching Business Education and their impact on alleviating unemployment. Ideally, Business Education students should graduate with strong employability and entrepreneurial abilities (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). The field covers areas like accounting, marketing, office technology, and entrepreneurship, aiming to provide learners with hands-on skills for starting their own ventures or securing jobs in companies. However, many graduates continue to struggle with finding employment because of deficiencies in their skills, stemming from outdated and insufficient training. Ongoing worries exist about how well the curricula, teaching methods, and resources in the state's higher education institutions match the constantly changing requirements of the contemporary job market and the developing demands of entrepreneurship. A properly designed Business Education program can

Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

deliver the necessary skills and knowledge to address these challenges. Given the adoption of advanced tools in workplaces, Business Education must ready students to perform effectively and productively in future business settings.

Although the guiding principle of Business Education programme is to provide individuals with appropriate knowledge, skills and competencies to be self-reliant and economically self-sufficient for gainful employment in the labour market, meaningful living, and to play a contributory role in development of the society. In line with this thought, much success has been achieved at the tertiary level of education in Nigeria, however there is still the need to focus more attention on aligning students of business education with the skills demanded in the industrial sector. Business Education programme needs to be formulated in consonance with the needs of the business ecosystem; and to further ensure that education and training offered are consistent with the competencies for the present and dynamic job requirements and opportunities. This can be achieved when tertiary institutions form collaboration with relevant industries which is a strategic tool in mitigating unemployment. This symbiotic relationship (institution-industry collaboration) would afford graduates to convert acquired knowledge into practice after graduation thereby leading to industrialization and technological development in the society. Nevertheless, tertiary institutions in Delta state have produced many graduates who have been found competent and productive in various areas of specialization, however, observations from labour market portray some graduates of business education are considered by their employers as half-baked or ill-prepared for the labour demands due to skill gaps in job performance. Business education is a key to manpower development and a critical tool in mitigating unemployment.

Hence, this study examined business education teaching strategies as correlates of unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Unemployment among Business Education graduates in Delta State has reached a worrisome level, despite supposed exposure to employability and entrepreneurial skills. This paradox suggests a disconnection between academic training and labor market needs. Several Business Education graduates seems to lack the practical skills and innovative thinking required for self-employment or gainful engagement in a competitive job market. Preliminary observations indicate that many tertiary institutions still rely heavily on traditional lecture methods, with minimal integration of modern teaching strategies such as entrepreneurship development, hands-on business projects, ICT applications, and industrial collaboration. Also, in a visit to some tertiary institutions, it was found that most business education students graduate from higher institutions without the experiential learning necessary to thrive independently. What could be the possible remedy to these challenges? In order to find solutions to these problems, the researcher studied Business Education teaching strategies as correlates of unemployment mitigation among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine Business Education teaching strategies as correlates of unemployment mitigation among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Determine the extent to which practical skills acquisition strategies correlate with employability skills of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.
2. Ascertain the extent to which the use of ICT-based instructional strategies correlates with the entrepreneurial intention of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.
3. Examine the correlation between the inclusion of entrepreneurship content in the curriculum and the rate of self-employment among recent graduates.
4. Identify the most effective business education strategy for employment mitigation in the Delta State Context.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does practical skills acquisition strategies correlate with employability skills of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?
2. To what extent does the use of ICT-based instructional strategies correlate with the entrepreneurial intention of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?
3. To what extent does entrepreneurship training strategy correlate with rate of self/hired employment among recent graduates of business education?
4. To what extent does components of business education strategy (practical skills acquisition strategies, ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurship strategies) mitigate unemployment among business education graduates in Delta State?
5. To what extent does practical skills acquisition strategies correlate unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?
6. To what extent does ICT-based instructional strategies correlate unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?

Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

7. To what extent does entrepreneurship training strategy correlate unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: Components of business education strategy (practical skills acquisition strategies, ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurship strategies) do not significantly mitigate unemployment among business education graduates in Delta State

H₀₂: There is no significant correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

H₀₃: There is no significant correlation between ICT-based instructional strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

H₀₄: There is no significant correlation between entrepreneurship training strategy and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

3.0 RESEARCH METHOD AND PROCEDURE

This chapter delineates the methodological framework employed to investigate Business Education teaching strategies and unemployment mitigation in Delta State tertiary institutions, encompassing the research design, population, sample and sampling techniques, research instrument, validation and reliability processes, data collection methods, and data analysis procedures. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, deemed appropriate as Nworgu (2015) indicates it effectively captures individual opinions, views, and attitudes without variable manipulation, thereby facilitating the systematic collection and interpretation of data to understand current phenomena and guide future studies. The target population comprised 1,028 respondents, consisting of 120 graduates and 908 Business Education students from four tertiary institutions: Delta State University, Abraka; University of Delta, Agbor; College of Education, Mosogar; and College of Education, Warri. A sample size of 397 respondents was determined for the study, utilizing stratified random sampling to select 277 students and a purposive sampling technique to select 120 graduates, ensuring adequate representation of the target groups. The research instrument was a 60-item structured questionnaire titled "Business Education Teaching Strategies and Unemployment Mitigation Questionnaire (BETSAUMQ)," structured into demographic and opinion-based sections utilizing a 4-point rating scale (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree, or Very High Extent to Very Low Extent) to measure the degree of agreement or extent of the variables. The instrument underwent face and content validation by three experts, two from the Department of Business Education and one from the Measurement and Evaluation Unit of Delta State University, Abraka, who reviewed the items for coverage and relevance, leading to necessary refinements. Reliability was established using the Cronbach Alpha method to determine internal consistency through a pilot study of 30 students at the University of Benin, Edo State; this yielded reliability coefficients ranging from 0.71 to 0.79 for the various sub-scales, with an overall coefficient of 0.74, confirming the instrument was reliable. Data collection involved the researcher and four briefed research assistants visiting the institutions to administer the questionnaires directly to respondents, ensuring copies were checked for completeness upon retrieval, which resulted in a 100% return rate of 397 copies. Data analysis utilized SPSS version 24, employing descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer research questions, and inferential statistics for hypothesis testing at a 0.05 level of significance; specifically, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used for testing Hypotheses 1 to 3, and Multivariate Linear Regression Analysis was used for Hypothesis 4, with a decision rule to reject the null hypothesis where the P-value is less than 0.05.

4.0 PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study are tabulated as follows:

Table 1: Pearson's Correlation of practical skills acquisition strategies and employability skills of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

Variables	N	Pearson's r	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies	397	.872	.000	Very High positive relationship
Employability Skills				

Data presented in Table 1 showed the correlation coefficients between practical skills acquisition strategies and employability skills of Business Education students. A calculated Pearson's r value of .872 was obtained for the variables. Since the r value falls within .71 –1.00 and it is positive, it shows that there is a very highly positive relationship between practical skills acquisition strategies and employability skills. Therefore, there is a very highly positive correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and employability skills of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

Table 2: Pearson’s Correlation of ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurial intention of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

Variables	N	Pearson’s r	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
ICT-based Instructional Strategies				
Entrepreneurial Intention	397	.576	.000	High positive relationship

Data presented in Table 2 revealed the correlation coefficients between ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurial intention of business education students. A calculated Pearson’s r value of .576 was obtained for the variables. Since the r value falls within .51 – .70 and it is positive, it shows that there is a high positive relationship between ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, there is a high positive correlation between ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurial intention of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

Table 3: Pearson’s Correlation of entrepreneurship training strategy correlate and rate of self/hired employment among recent graduates of business education

Variables	N	Pearson’s r	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Entrepreneurship Training Strategy				
Self/Hired Employment	397	.626	.000	High positive relationship

Data presented in Table 3 revealed the correlation coefficients Entrepreneurship Training Strategy and rate of Self/Hired Employment of business education students. A calculated Pearson’s r value of .626 was obtained for the variables. Since the r value falls within .51 – .70 and it is positive, it shows that there is a high positive relationship between ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, there is a high positive correlation between Entrepreneurship Training Strategy and rate of Self/Hired Employment of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

Table 4: Regression Model Summary of Components of business education strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education graduates in Delta State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.758 ^a	.575	.571	.532

a. Predictors: (Constant), Entrepreneurship Strategy, ICT-Based Instructional Strategies, Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies

Table 4 showed a calculated R value of .758 and R square value of .575 meaning that components of business education strategies accounts for 57.5% of unemployment mitigation among business education graduates in Delta State.

Table 5: Regression ANOVA of components of business education strategies and unemployment mitigation

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	50.799	3	16.933	31.554	.000 ^b
	Residual	210.360	392	.537		
	Total	261.159	395			

a. Dependent Variable: Unemployment Mitigation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Entrepreneurship Strategy, ICT-Based Instructional Strategies, Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies

Table 5 indicated that a calculated F value of 31.554 and a P value of .000, testing at an alpha level of .05. The P-value is less than the alpha level, hence the null hypothesis which states that components of business education strategies do not significantly mitigate unemployment among business education graduates in Delta State was rejected. Consequently, components of business education strategies mitigate unemployment among business education graduates in Delta State.

Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

Table 6: Regression Coefficients of components of business education strategies and unemployment mitigation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.746	.218		3.417	.001
Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies	.209	.053	.192	3.923	.000
ICT-Based Instructional Strategies	.049	.044	.053	1.122	.263
Entrepreneurship Training Strategy	.387	.056	.329	6.906	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Unemployment Mitigation

Table 6 revealed for Practical skills acquisition strategies a p-value of .000, for ICT-Based Instructional Strategies a p-value of .263 and for Entrepreneurship Training Strategy, a p-value of .000. From the above result only two of the components which are practical skills acquisition strategies and entrepreneurship training strategy significantly mitigate unemployment with beta values of .192 and .329 accounting for 19.2%, and 32.9% respectively of unemployment mitigation of business education graduates.

Table 7: Pearson r on Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies and Unemployment Mitigation

		Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies	Unemployment Mitigation
Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	.575**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	397	397
Unemployment Mitigation	Pearson Correlation	.575**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	397	397

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 showed that Practical Skills Acquisition Strategies has highly positive relationship with unemployment Mitigation with $r = .575$. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions was rejected. Thus, there is a significant correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

Table 8: Pearson r on ICT-based instructional strategies and Unemployment Mitigation

		ICT-based instructional strategies	Unemployment Mitigation
ICT-based instructional strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	.580**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	397	397
Unemployment Mitigation	Pearson Correlation	.580**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	397	397

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 8 disclosed that ICT-based instructional strategies has highly positive relationship with unemployment Mitigation with $r = .580$. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant correlation between ICT-based instructional strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions was rejected. Thus, there is a significant correlation between ICT-based instructional strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

Table 9: Pearson r on Entrepreneurship Training Strategy and Unemployment Mitigation

		Entrepreneurship Training Strategy	Unemployment Mitigation
Entrepreneurship Training Strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	.644**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	397	397
Unemployment Mitigation	Pearson Correlation	.644**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	397	397

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 9 exhibited that Entrepreneurship Training Strategy has highly positive relationship with unemployment Mitigation with $r = .644$. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant correlation between Entrepreneurship Training Strategy and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions was rejected. Thus, there is a significant correlation between Entrepreneurship Training Strategy and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

4.1 Discussion of Findings

The finding of research question one portrayed that there was a very highly positive correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and employability skills of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. This implied that students who excel in acquiring hands-on, practical skills are also very likely to possess strong, in-demand general work skills. This findings agreed with the recommendation of Iyoha and Umeh (2024) that business education programme should be linked with employers of labour and industries to give business education students practical knowledge of the world of work and work-ready on graduation. Also, the finding is in line with Nnamaka (2024) that specialized simulations that replicate industries like finance, marketing, or supply chain management give students practical experience in their chosen field. The finding further corroborate that of Akpojotor (2025) who found that there was no significant difference in the mean response of male and female respondents on problem solving and critical thinking skills required in improving business education graduates employability skills for engagement and sustainable future in Delta State. The finding further support that of Dahiru and Shua (2023) who found that there was no significant difference in the average responses between male and female graduates of the Office Technology Management program in Borno state regarding the extent of influence of curriculum content and the employability skills.

The findings of research question two divulged that there was a high positive correlation between ICT-based instructional strategies and entrepreneurial intention of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. This implied that effective integration and use of ICT in teaching is strongly associated with students' desire and likelihood to start their own businesses. In essence, the correlation suggests that technology is a vital catalyst in transforming a student's passive academic knowledge into an active desire to launch a business venture. This finding is in harmony with the findings of Ubulom and Meshack (2024) that Business Education students highly valued the soft skills and ICT skills they acquired to reduce unemployment.

The finding of research question three disclosed that there is a high positive correlation between Entrepreneurship Training Strategy and rate of Self/Hired Employment of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. This implied that an effective entrepreneurship training likely leads to better employment outcomes for those students. In other words, a high positive correlation suggests that as the quality, intensity, or relevance of the entrepreneurship training strategies increases, the rate of employment (both self-employment and being hired) also tends to increase significantly. This finding harmonized that of Onuma (2016) who found a significant correlation between entrepreneurial education and postgraduate job generation and that entrepreneurship education is more vital to students in terms of equipping them with skills for postgraduate job generation potential than to job seeker.

The finding of hypothesis one revealed that components of business education strategies mitigate unemployment among business education graduates in Delta State. This implied that specific parts of the way business education is planned and carried out are effective in reducing the rate of joblessness among business education graduates in Delta State. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Emaziye and Oroka (2024) who found that female and male business education lecturers agreed that digital and entrepreneurial skills curb youth unemployment in Delta State.

The findings of hypothesis two showed that there was a significant correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. This implied that when students acquire skills that are directly applicable to job market demands, they are more likely to find employment or create their own job. This findings is in agreement with the findings of Ezeani and Okolocha (2020) emphasized that integrating practical training and industry collaborations significantly enhances students' job prospects. Also, the finding is in line with that of Okolie, Nwosu, and Mlanga (2019) who found in their study that students exposed to practical business courses had higher employment rates due to enhanced competencies.

Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

In hypothesis three, it was found that there was a significant correlation between ICT-based instructional strategies and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. This implied that there is a strong and statistically reliable connection between using ICT in teaching and a reduction in unemployment as students who are taught with ICT are graduates who are better equipped for the modern job market, thereby lowering joblessness. The finding harmonized that of Hesda (2023) that ICT development leads to a decrease in total unemployment.

In hypothesis four, it was found that there was a significant correlation between Entrepreneurship Training Strategy and unemployment mitigation among business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. This means that means that teaching students to be entrepreneurs is a reliable way to solve the problem of joblessness. The finding harmonized that of Okoro (2024) that Entrepreneurship education is significantly relevant in eradicating unemployment/poverty and for creating employment. Also, the finding agreed with the findings of Jiddah (2016) that entrepreneurial career aspirations have a significant impact on graduates' business start-up.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that there was a very highly positive correlation between practical skills acquisition strategies and employability skills of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. Also that components of business education teaching strategies (practical skills acquisition strategies, ICT-based instructional strategies, and entrepreneurship training strategies) mitigate unemployment among business education graduates in Delta State. However, it was further concluded that the most significant components that mitigate unemployment are practical skills acquisition and entrepreneurship training strategies. This implies that Practical Skills Acquisition and Entrepreneurship Training are highly effective strategies for mitigating unemployment among business education students because the focus shifted from job-seeking to job-readiness and job-creation. Also, the strategies focus on equipping students with tangible, market-relevant abilities that meet current industry demands, thereby increasing their immediate employability or capacity for self-employment.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation are made:

1. Stakeholders of business education programme should ensure that the student are properly engaged in practical training as it will boost their practical skills acquisition and invariably boost their employability skills which in turn will help to mitigate unemployment.
2. Business Education Lecturers should ensure that they teacher the business education students using ICT-based instructional strategies since it helps to increase the business education students' entrepreneurial intention.
3. Management of tertiary institutions should ensure that they continue to emphasis Entrepreneurship Training Strategy as a means of training the business education students, since it boost the rate of Self/Hired Employment of business education students.

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Business Education Teaching Strategies as Correlate of Unemployment Mitigation Among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

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